

Literary Clichés and the Age of Revolution

A brief explanation of society development

Introduction

Many people who watch movies or read literary works (hereafter works; I will use the latter term in my manuscript to refer not only to the work in its traditional meaning but also to a myth which was adapted by artists, a screenplay, etc.) may notice a constant repetition of some scenes and episodes. If you type in the browser search bar the phrase “Clichés¹ in movies,” it becomes clear that this phenomenon is familiar to the fans of the action genre. Literature scholars have defined literary cliché as: an idea, event, or detail that is used so often in literature or film that it becomes predictable and even boring (MasterClass, 2021). Now I am very surprised because under these circumstances, the amount of clichés in the works has not been properly evaluated and researched as it is possible. Someone may dispute this conclusion of mine by mentioning Joseph Campbell’s overly hyped “A Hero with a Thousand Faces.” In that case, I would reply that such a work cannot be accepted as a scholarly study of the mentioned problem (I would rather call it a hymn glorifying psychoanalysis), since it even does not contain a structured set of clichés that we usually find in writings. If a reader of this essay wants to get an idea about the last concept, he/she should use the well-known “Morphology of the Folktale” (Propp, 1968). For those who do not know what I am talking about, Vladimir Propp, in his research in the first half of the 20th century, found that all folktales within a certain class of fairy tales have a unique structure of character actions (“Functions of dramatis personae”). Today, scholars would say that all these folktales obviously derive from some archetype; but for us it is important that Propp is the first to use the differential calculus (i.e. the notes on the elementary actions of the characters in a text of the work in this case), which belongs to mathematics, for the study of literature, although Propp himself did not know it. This is the result: Our study of the set of clichés in the works can reach a fundamentally new level at the moment, because a scientific theory (according to Steven Hawking, it is construction in our imagination that is purposed to explain the set of phenomena with a minimal number of entered parameters and provide us with predictions that can be tested with experiments or observations) can only gain by using mathematics. Continuing to talk about scientific works that can be useful for the exploration of clichés, I would also like to mention the article “The emotional arcs of stories are dominated by six basic shapes” (Reagan, Mitchell, Danforth & Sheridan Dodds, 2016): with it we have macro-level exploration of plot in works.

The initial methods of the set of clichés research

The single action of character

When reading our favorite books or watching movies and documentaries, the single character actions (further actions), which have at least three repetitions in independent sources (such as the works created by competing authors almost simultaneously, the works of authors belonging to the Free World, and the works of dissidents from countries behind the Iron Curtain, and so on.). Independent sources are needed in this case to minimize the influence of Human Factor (thus, “Avatar” (Cameron, 2009) and “Skyline” (Strause & Strause, 2010), the movies, have at least one essentially identical scene: it is set in the battle episodes)). And what the very first scene we should know? Well, I am always very impressed by scene that can be called “Hero/heroine jumps down from the edge of waterfall” (such an unplanned cliff jump was seen in “Avatar”), to get some practice in recognizing the actions, let us dissect it. This is the result: We will get some ideas about such actions: “The enemy pursues hero/heroine,” “Hero/heroine suddenly finds himself on the edge of waterfall,” “Hero/heroine jumps down from the edge of the waterfall,” and “Hero/heroine escapes.” It is clear to see that the differentiation of the work is not very difficult. And in the same way we can see the actions in real life, not only in the scenes of the works. In this case, we see how the action “Hero/heroine punishes a strong enemy who is insolent” is manifested:

In some time, a giant centipede killed a careless mouse by using poison;

In 1828, an adult male sperm whale, under the influence of hormone testosterone (it was sperm whale breeding season), smashed the whaling schooner “Essex,” which at the time of the event had not yet been repaired after storm;

In 1879, several thousands of Zulu warriors armed mainly with spears destroyed the British infantry battalion whose camp had not been made into a fortress.

An attentive reader can see that these examples can also be presented as manifestations of the action “The enemy defeats hero/heroine by using deceit.” So, we can assume that many manifestations of the actions refer to the two antagonistic characters (just as square root generally has two solutions) - but this phenomenon must not be confused with the influence of the actions on each other (when combined actions are formed). So we have already got an idea of the single character actions. Next, within the framework of this theory of repeated elements in the works, we must pay attention to the nature of the character (it can be either positive or negative), although Vladimir Propp, researching the class of folk tales, as a morphologist of the folk tale, had no need to perform such action.

¹ It must be realized that literary clichés in common are only “The top of iceberg” when we talk about the set of repeated elements – many of which are not quite recognizable due to their rareness - in the works.

The principle of exclusion

Some readers may ask, “How are we to interpret a manifestation of the action as it simultaneously relates to the two antagonistic characters?” The principle of exclusion should help us in this case. It must be explained that this theory is based on linear logic so that the spheres of action of protagonist and antagonist cannot overlap. Thus, when we encounter the mentioned appearance, we will automatically get two meanings (one of which refers to Form and the other to Content) at that moment.

The simplest episode (it consists only of two the character actions)

Coming back to the description of the initial methods of the set of clichés research, I must say that in the study of literature we must make the integration since it [the integration] is the next step after the differentiation. The essence of the integration in this case is that we must put together all the actions we have obtained via differentiation (like a puzzle), on condition that they do not contradict each other. This is the main task of this theory (therefore the picture we will get may differ from real life). And the very first step on this way can be the creation of the simplest episode consisting only of two the character actions (another episode) - these actions can belong either to a single character or to two different characters. In this case, it is very convenient to explore the episode “Hero/heroine gets the help of a friend, and then enemy punishes the friend” (this action is not rare and could be seen in the film “The Thirty-Nine Steps” (Sharp, 1978)). Someone may ask, “Why only two actions?” Then I would say that if we remember the Three-body problem (it belongs to astronomy), we will understand that such condition was established because of Chaos theory. Now I propose to accept the help that graphic schemes deliver as the initial methods of the set of repeated elements in the works had already been discussed.

The graphic scheme for transmission the change in the protagonist state during the narration

After the aforementioned paper of mathematicians team (Reagan, Mitchell, Danforth & Sheridan Dodds, 2016) had been read, let’s take a look on the plot shape “Cinderella” since it is the most popular plot archetype among readers (Fig 1, a) – it must be added only that I consider the latter phenomenon to be the combination of such concepts: “Man on hill” and “Man in a hole,” which is the antipode of previous one, the basic plot shapes (Fig 1, b).

Figure 1 (Image: Yaremko)

To be able to move further, I should report that there are at least two variations of the basic plot shape “Man in a hole” exist. The first version (Fig 2) can be described with this: The protagonist suddenly is freed (Resolution) after he/she had been being imprisoned or in captivity (Inciting incident) for a long time – although the actions of hero needed for the latter to become free can be shown, emphasis is put on a long being in discomfort (such works as “The Showshen Redemption” (Darabont, 1994), “District 9” (Blomkamp, 2009), the movies, “Flight of the Earth” (Carsac, 1960), the novel, in common are good illustration of these words of mine; if we observe real life, then our attention must be paid to the 1990’s restoring of the independence of Baltic states and how the territorial completeness of Azerbaijan was restored in 2023).

Another variation of the mentioned plot shape usually shows how the protagonist gradually “pushes-off the obstacle” – we are talking about the opponents are getting neutralized, one by one; the defeat of the main villain can be considered as Resolution in this case (Fig 3). “Cliffhanger” (Harlin, 1993), “North Star” (Gaup, 1996), “Apocalipto” (Gibson, 2004), “Tale of the Mummy” (Mulcahy, 1998), and “Peppermint” (Morel, 2018), the movies, can show my rightness.

Figure 2 (Image: Yaremko)

Figure 3 (Image: Yaremko)

There is the graph we need for our task to be resolved below (Fig 4) – as it can be seen I chose the first variant of “Man in a hole” (it is supposed that second one will be useful for us further). I want to add that it is illustrated by the set of disastrous events in human history (Fig 5).

Figure 4 (Image: Yaremko)

No	Segment C - D	Segment E - F	Segment F - G1	Segment G1 - H
1	The pairs of elementary particles and their antiparticles were formed after the Big Bang	The pairs of elementary particles and their antiparticles annihilated after certain expansion of the Universe	Only about 0.0001 percent of the original number of elementary particles survived due to the Baryon asymmetry exists in the Universe	
2	The massive and unstable stars of the first generation were formed	The stars of the first generation relatively simultaneously exploded after a relatively short period of existing		Much more stable, due to the presence of heavy metals, the stars of the second generation were formed
3	The mammals and the dinosaurs almost simultaneously were formed	The mammals got the dominance of the dinosaurs	The mammals survived underground (which was their habitat for more than 150 million years)	The mammals came to the Earth's surface after the dinosaurs became extinct
4	The diversification of organisms on Earth (generally the dinosaurs) took place	Most of organisms on Earth (generally the dinosaurs) died out after the falling of the Chicxulub asteroid	Some species of organisms that belonged with different classes (mammals, birds, lizards, etc.) survived underground	The diversification of organisms on Earth (generally the mammals) took place
5	The people of the modern type begun to settle outside Africa	New occupants faced the mass-extinction caused by the eruption of the Toba volcano	Literally a few the humans of the modern type which had been living outside Africa survived	The people of the modern type continued their settling outside Africa

Figure 5 (Image: Yaremko)

I think some readers will be interested in the identity of the protagonist of Fig 4 after reading Fig 5. To find this identity, we need to interpret the amount of characters in the works.

The characters

I had been researching the works for almost eighteen years when I came to the conclusion that, in general, there are at most three pairs of defining characters in society: a master and an enemy of the master; a traitor to the master and a helper of the master; people and the remnant of the people. I must say that the interpretation of the characters becomes much easier if we assume that Ruler means the phenomenon of the highest level - generally Law (another name is Order). Then Chaos automatically becomes the enemy (this is very convenient for us because at the moment we have a solid foundation of classical thermodynamics). Having seen the first pair of characters, it is necessary to add to what has been said that only Law governs society (people) because of level of location. Right now the question is, "Who is this traitor?" I am confident that this person is the collective First Servant of Law (Servant 1) - the collection of charismatic revolution leaders with remarkable will and intellect unable to complete the main task of revolution; this conclusion emerges from Fig 6 which is using the data of Fig 4.

No	Segment C - D	Segment E - F
1	During the English Revolution, Oliver Cromwell fought against King Charles I to bring an end to the latter's abuse of power	Oliver Cromwell made himself Lord Protector
2	At the starting of the French Revolution Maximilian Robespierre fought tyranny	Maximilian Robespierre became a tyrant
3	During the French Revolution Napoleon Bonaparte fought against the enemies of the Revolution	Napoleon Bonaparte made himself emperor

Figure 6 (Image: Yaremko)

I continue to interpret characters, and I want to say that the helper is the collective Second Servant of Law (Servant 2) which is the collection of principled people in the society (these are often dissidents). So the remnant remains (sorry for the tautology) - it is clear that it points directly to mass extinction in the society during a major crisis. Now I would like to continue this section, and I must say in this case that we can see that the mentioned trajectory on Fig 4 primarily reflects the change of the status of Law in the society over time, as the main determining personalities of human society have already gotten known to us.

A new theory of repeated elements can be successfully used but with some limitations

An attentive reader looking at Fig 6 could see that Servant 1 can be narrated only with the beginning of the Age of revolution - so this theory has a limited probability of application and works only on the basis of the Monopoly on violence. I drew this conclusion because rulers at the beginning of civilization (like Hammurabi), who are the first to present written law codes to people, cannot be presented as First Servants of Law due to the motives they had - primarily the usurpation of power in the society and the personal enrichment.

Fractals

Figure 7 (Image: Yaremko)

Since we have come across the term “Management” twice dealing with the actions in the works (as we said, Law governs the society with elected authority), we can say that at the moment we are dealing with fractals (these are the objects that look like their parts). So, as we can see, the authority in the society is the fractal reflection of Law; I transfer this phenomenon with Fig 7 (as we know, a tree is one of the manifestations of fractals). We can also say that the mentioned presence of two meanings for the many manifestations of the actions is the fractal reflection of the presence of two antagonistic forces - the order and chaos; I can add to what has been said that in the future (we are going to get the studying of society development by using the set of clichés done) we should come across many fractal reflections.

The law of equilibrium

The issue of power will not let me go - it's just a joke. But right now the question is, “Why does First Servant always distribute the resources of the society in the first phase of revolution, not Second Servant?” If we remember the Second law of thermodynamics (it says that chaos has the greatest probability of spontaneous realization, not order), we will see a similar picture (so the beginning of the Big Bang is singularity). The reason for this is the existence of Law of equilibrium, which states that the negative determiner usually has some physical advantage over the opponent. The formulation for this law is: The sum of moral and physical properties for each determinant in the society is constanta ($A+B=constanta$). It is not difficult to show that Chaos, if not endowed with allurements of illicit pleasures, is not able to realize its destructive role in society; there is a similar case: If Servant 1 has no extraordinary charisma and personality to be attractive in society, Servant 2 has no imprisonment because of his/her loyalty to Law - which is usually unreal.

The events of the society development

Prehistory (segment A - D)

It must be said that this passage provides the only opportunity to see the First Service to Law, albeit schematically (it is only reconstruction), before the rebellion against Order made by Servant 1. The reason for this is that First Service is reflected only fragmentarily in the works, since “history is always written by winners” and there is simply no room for losers in all works, which constantly glorify the Second Service. Even tragedies, such as the film “Tale of the Mummy” (Mulcahy, 1998), cannot be exceptions to this rule, even if they do not show the triumph of Servant 2. If literary fans want to see these few relics of the First Service in works, they should pay attention first and foremost to prologue, which often depicts the hero's happy life (as in the movie “Peppermint” (Morel, 2018)); then attention should be paid to the character memories of the villain's positive activities before his/her moral decline (a good example of this is Gus Conroy's account of the happy life his wife Arlene led until she fell under the power of the Objects after finding the key to a nonexistent room 10 - TV series “Lost Room” (Harkcom & Baxley, 2006) is meant). Now I want to mention the episode “Hero/heroine brings down the enemy, and then the enemy rises” - in this case, it is very useful to describe how Servant 1, under the influence of a strong emotional impulse, takes a relatively short period of time to use the Method of punishment and reward to make the society formally serve Law

(segment C - D in Fig 4; the situation for Chaos on it can be described by the action “The criminal goes to the jail” (we can see it through the arrest of Lord Blackwood in the movie “Sherlock Holmes”).

First Servant makes the rebellion (point D)

Figure 8 (Image: Yaremko)

Point D on Fig 8 marks that moment when the desire for illicit pleasures is revealed (in this case such desire is some kind of a potential barrier on the way Law to get the victory in the struggle against Chaos). It must be said that Servant 1 at this moment feels the fear of losing the power over society, and the mentioned fear can be seen through the desire to illegally stay in the power - but all the social groups themselves, tired of keeping an eye on Law, do not pay the special attention to these events. The action “A fugitive sees his/her foot (hair, clothes, etc.) that is stuck on the obstacle” - seen in the finale of the film “Mortal Engines” (Rivers, 2018) - confirms my words very well; it can also help to understand the events from Fig 8, in which the distortion of the trajectories of change in the levels of the respect which Servant 1 and Servant 2 give Order is shown. If the reader is interested in the origin of this concept (I am now focusing on the aforementioned distortion of the trajectories), I will say that I have borrowed it from the diagram, which is able to show the change in the velocity of a physical body over time when that body is under the influence of a constant force (Fig 9); and it [the diagram] can represent the speed of light in vacuum as the potential barrier that cannot be reached by physical bodies (but not by some elementary particles).

Figure 9 (Image: Yaremko)

Another example of the potential barrier is the force of the electromagnetic repulsion between two protons - only the interiors of stars has such temperature that the mentioned potential barrier can be overcome (it must be understood that both the light of stars and the life on planets are not possible without overcoming this barrier).

Servant 2 counters the opponent (segment D - E)

If we go to Fig 8 for learning about Second Servant’s activities, we will see that while Traitor tries to realize the ambitions for power, Servant 2, being inspired by the example of the predecessor, is ignoring temptations of Chaos and actively promoting Law in the society (segment D - E of Fig 8). As a result, Servant 2 is able to keep the opponent from realizing Servant 1’s coup attempt for some time, but he/she is doomed to stop doing so for the fear of the First Servant’s revenge (section E - F of Fig 8). So, the First Servant (which essence is the fear of punishment after bad deeds and the desire for reward after good deeds) is not able to give Law the achievement of the goal that this person needs - total downfall of chaos in the society in the long run (the action “Hero/heroine has the failure,” which can be seen in the movie “Romancing the stone” (Zemeckis, 1984) - in this case I am pointing to the failed attempt of the protagonist to climb a tower - can confirm the last words very well).

The complete usurpation of power in the society (segment E - F)

Figure 10 (Image: Yaremko)

If we now return to the activities of Servant 1, we will see that this person, in order to have the unlimited power over society, takes the place in the society that was intended for Law - it means that Chaos becomes essentially free in the society (the works depict this phenomenon with such actions: “A criminal bribes policeman” (an example of a common corruption) and “A criminal escapes from prison” - this is illustrated by Fig 10, which graphically depicts the change in statuses of Servant 1 and Chaos in the society over time (I obtained the diagram of status change for Chaos by using the same concept for Order).

Helper gets the revenge of the opponent (segment F - F1)

Figure 11 (Image: Yaremko)

If we pay attention to Fig 11 at this moment (which shows the change of the status of Second Servant in the society over time), then we will additionally see the imprisonment of Servant 2 after the cowardice and betrayal of Law shown by this person. As you can now imagine, the described decline in living standards is the result of the usurper’s revenge. Fig 12 can show how this happened more than once in history (just follow blue lines on graphs).

No	Segment D - E (Fig 8)	Segment E - F (Fig 8)	Segment F - F1 (Fig 11)
1	Crown prince Dan of the Yan state arranged the attempt on the life of King Zhen of the Qin state to prevent a possible usurpation of the domain	Jin Ke, the assassin, could not accomplish the task	King Zhen of the Qin state invaded the Yan state to seek revenge
2	Ishida Mitsunari tried to stop the Tokugawa Ieyasu's arising after Toyotomi Hideyoshi died	Ishida Mitsunari lost the Battle of Sekigahara	Ishida Mitsunari was executed by the order of Tokugawa Ieyasu
3	Great Britain and France tried to stop the revanchism of Germany after that country attacked Poland	The British and French army units were encircled at Dunkirk	France was occupied and Great Britain was bombed by the armies of Nazi Germany
4	Yulia Tymoshenko tried to defeat Viktor Yanukovich in the 2010 presidential election	Yulia Tymoshenko lost the 2010 presidential election	Yulia Tymoshenko was imprisoned for political reasons by Viktor Yanukovich's initiative

Figure 12 (Image: Yaremko)

Next, if we pay attention to the change of the status of Order, we see that the decrease of Second Servant's standard of living means that Law should have a minimum number of followers in the society (at this moment it becomes clear why the status of the master does not reach the mark 0 (level 0) on the Amplitude axis during the described fall, when Servant 1 makes the revolt) - so in this case we see how the action "Servant sacrifices the life for the master to live" (which is very common) is revealed.

The interpretation of the action "A servant sacrifices the life for the master to live"

Now, that we have some idea of Second Servant's loyalty to the master, let us look again at Fig 11. We can see on it three times the concept of "Death" - in two cases this concept has a symbolic meaning ("The death of the master" in this theory means the lowering of Law's status in society, and "The death of hero/heroine" means the lowering of Second Servant's standard of living) and in the only case - a real meaning (so Servant 1 must be killed (executed) or imprisoned until the end of life). So, the action I mentioned can be represented as the combination of such actions: "The enemy harms hero/heroine" and "The enemy dies." This is because on our planet the mortal physical life of organisms consisting of billions of cells is fractal reflection of the moral activities of Servant 1 among other explanations (segment A - E of Fig 8).

Master should get all the loyalty (segment F - G1)

This longest event can be described by the action "Hero/heroine damages the chain with saw" (as in the movie "Captain America: The Winter Soldier" (Russo & Russo, 2014) during the fight in elevator Steve Rogers rips a magnetic bracelet from the wall) – I am talking about the process of overcoming the potential barrier of the temptation of illicit pleasures by Second Servant with completely ignoring the threats of Traitor (Fig 13 (remember that Chaos is the antagonist)).

No	Segment C - D (Fig 10, gray line)	Segment E - F (Fig 10, gray line)	Segment F - G (Fig 8, blue line)
1	The National Convention arrested Maximilian Robespierre and the most of his counterparts	The group of Maximilian Robespierre was freed by the supporters	The military defeated Maximilian Robespierre's supporters
2	The Anti-Napoleon coalition army defeated Napoleon's army in the "Battle of the Nations" near Leipzig	Napoleon Bonaparte fled island of Elba	The Anti-Napoleon coalition army defeated Napoleon's army near the village of Waterloo
3	The Entente countries defeated Germany in WWI	Europe lost its advantage over Germany after WWI	The Anti-Hitler Coalition defeated Nazi Germany in WWII
4	The Orange Revolution of 2005 stopped the Viktor Yanukovich's trying to become the President of Ukraine	Viktor Yanukovich became the President of Ukraine in 2010	The protesters at Independence Square in Kyiv-city defeated the Viktor Yanukovich's criminal regime in 2014

Figure 13 (Image: Yaremko)

What does the criminal regime of Servant 1 (which generally includes the society) expect after such acts of Helper? If we look at the segment E - F on Fig 8, we see that Traitor is very careful and tries to avoid conflicts with powerful actors (e.g. society), but the political repression against the opponent gradually drives him/her directly into the "Arms of chaos". Based on the last explanation, Second Servant's activities during this period can represent the action "Hero/heroine makes the weapon" (in this case, I like the scene from the movie "Anthropoid" (Ellis, 2016), where German soldiers prepare their machine gun to fire), which belongs to a large family of actions (which are all actions of characters that are essentially similar; the concept of "Family of actions" follows directly from Propp's

concept of “Functions of dramatis personae”) which can be named “Hero/heroine makes the tool for salvation” (it can be said that Fig 3 is seen at this moment).

Traitor meets total collapse (segment G1 - H)

The roots of the fall of Servant 1 lie in point G, where two events occur synchronously: Helper proves complete loyalty to Order and Chaos completely fills the mind of Servant 1 with itself (we obviously see at this moment the action “Hero/heroine strikes the enemy by latter’s own weapon,” which is also seen in the final battle of the movie “Silent Trigger” (Mulcahy, 1996)). As a result, First Servant has to start the war against the powerful person (this conflict (segment G - H), as it can be seen from Fig 4, is the fractal reflection of the Traitor’s rebellion against Law (segment F - H); I must add that if we think of the Ice Age, we will see that the conflict with the powerful person means the careless night departure of man/woman from the campfire directly to the hunting ground of sabre-toothed cats). At the beginning of this adventure, Traitor should receive some benefits, but it is certain that after reaching point G, the criminal regime is doomed. If we now return to Fig 4, we see that the status of Law increases very rapidly during the collapse because Usurper’s followers die out en masse (which event is symbolic or real). If we observe Fig 11, we see a gradual restoration of Servant 2’s status in the society (since only this person can fill power vacuum) and the beginning of a long process of restoration awaiting Remnant (this is shown with Fig 14).

Figure 14 (Image: Yaremko)

The explanation of the end of the First Service

Since we have already seen how the status of Law in the society can be restored by Order after the event of collapse, we can better understand why the First Service is always doomed to failure. Now the chaotic attempt at revanch can be clearly seen as the return to the state of equilibrium (Fig 15). This is because the methods used by Servant 1 to try to overcome chaos in the society are very similar to chaotic methods.

Figure 15 (Image: Yaremko)

Important conclusions

- Despotisms cannot succeed in economics and politics in the distant future, as each of them is simultaneously the counterpart and source of chaos;
- Countries that often act according to the Realpolitik principle cannot succeed economically and politically in the distant future, because each of them is the analogue of First Servant in the international arena;
- Countries that truly respect Law (which means avoiding the application of the Realpolitik principle) should succeed economically and politically in the long run;

Countries that want to be promoted by Law must experience the crisis of the First Service with all its consequences.

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